

Roundtable Discussion:

Social Science Funding and Knowledge Production During Turbulent Times: Reflections From MENA Scholars

Diana B. Greenwald in conversation with Lisa Anderson, Sofia Fenner, Ellen Lust, Jamil Mouawad, Salma Mousa

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Introduction, by Diana B. Greenwald

On October 2, 2025, we convened a virtual roundtable to discuss the state of funding for social science research in and on the MENA region. To reflect on this topic, we invited five scholars who are at various stages in their careers, whose work represents diverse epistemological and methodological approaches, and who have drawn on a range of types of resources to fund their work. An edited transcript of our conversation follows below.

One question that hovered over much of our conversation was: How exceptional is the present moment? Some of the challenges that scholars in our field face seem like stable, if not permanent, features of the landscape. We touch on these in our discussion: For example, the inevitable ways that politics, including donor priorities, shape research, and the sometimes frustrating role of other “gate-keepers”, such as institutional review

boards. Yet, recent months have also seen a rapid accumulation of acute shocks. In the US, in particular, MENA scholars have not been immune from the Trump administration’s jarring, multidimensional assault on academic research and higher education. President Trump has overseen the termination of National Science Foundation (NSF)-funded projects and reductions that, as of mid-2025, had brought scientific research awards in the US to [their lowest rate in decades](#). The National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) was similarly targeted for drastic cuts and [subsequent funding](#) was allocated to topics aligned with President Trump’s ideological agenda. The executive branch has [seized control of the United States Institute of Peace](#), which funded a well-known dissertation fellowship, among other things, and gutted its existing staff. Federal budget appropriations remain very much in flux as, at the time of

writing, the US is in its third week of a government shutdown. Scholars from select countries in the region – including Iran, Libya, Sudan, and Yemen – have been banned from entering the US [under a June 2025 executive order](#). Further, efforts by the US government, state governments, and academic institutions to surveil, control, and suppress speech and protest on Palestine has contributed to a climate of insecurity and fear, with particularly existential consequences for non-citizen and immigrant members of our community. Most of these actions and policies have been, and continue to be, challenged in court. In the meantime, we are all feeling these silencing pressure from above in different ways, and to varying degrees.

Our contributors reflect on what a potential longer term retreat in US funding might mean for individual scholars and knowledge production, more broadly. We agreed that those of us who have had the benefit of working in relatively open and unrestricted settings now have much to learn from those who have not. Despite an overall sense that the environment for field-based political science research in MENA has become more constrained in recent years, contributors emphasized how scholars might nonetheless navigate this environment and pursue strategic opportunities by, for example, exploring lesser-known sources of social science funding in the region; adopting a form of bricolage to draw on disparate resources, institutions, and relationships to support their research; turning to epistemological and methodological approaches that might be both lower cost and more resilient to political shocks (here, our contributors reflect on both interpretivist methods and the analysis of unstructured “big data”); and creatively redefining what constitutes “the field” when certain populations and geographies are inaccessible.

However, not all of these strategies – which call for nimbleness, flexibility, and creative retooling – are available to all scholars at all times. The way forward, as it emerges from our conversation, places significant burdens on researchers, and early-career and untenured scholars will be disproportionately affected.

Many scholars based in the region have become accustomed to navigating authoritarian institutions and practices, active conflict zones, and conditions of seemingly self-perpetuating volatility and crisis. As higher educational and research institutions in the MENA region have been either unable or unwilling to invest significantly in social science research, roundtable participants reflect on how MENA-based social scientists have increasingly turned to sources of non-academic research funding and the sometimes worrying implications of this trend. In addition to some of these more structural or slower moving trends in the region itself, certain equilibria seem to have been shattered in recent years. The war in Sudan, which began in April 2023, has been defined by atrocious war crimes, upending the lives of tens of millions of people, resulting in mass displacement, famine, and what has been described as [one of the largest humanitarian crises ever recorded](#). Following the October 7, 2023 Hamas-led attacks, Israel’s genocidal war in Gaza has devastated a people, laying waste to their cities and neighborhoods, their historic sites, their homes, their storefronts, their infrastructure, their universities, their places of worship, their farms, and their land. The expansion of Israel’s war fronts into Lebanon, Iran, Syria, Yemen, and even, for a moment, Qatar layered new destruction and instability on top of existing challenges and crises. It may be too early to catalog the myriad ways in which these events will shape scholarship

and knowledge production. Even as pages of documentation, archival material, theoretical advances, and new empirical findings are constructed in the months and years ahead, we may never know how much has been permanently lost.

Edited Transcript

Diana B. Greenwald (DG): I thought that we could begin this conversation on research funding by drawing on [a recent piece](#) that, Ellen, you've recently written on this topic, with Samuel Tafesse Wakuma, in the *Daedalus special issue* that was co-edited by Lisa with Rabab El-Mahdi and Seteney Shami. You've written this piece on the economics of social science research and knowledge production in the Middle East and North Africa. There are a number of findings from this dataset that you built and analyzed in the piece. One of the findings that stood out to me was that research funding coming from sources within the region is dwarfed by funding resources from outside the region. Also, the substance and nature of research seems to vary depending on the funding sources. So, I thought maybe the findings from this article could be a good launching point for our conversation. Ellen, do you want to summarize some of the key points there, and some of the arguments you develop about these differences in the origins of research funding and the implications that has for social science knowledge production?

Ellen Lust (EL): Sure, and I should preface this by saying that the kind of research funding that we're able to look at in this piece is primarily that given by large organizations like the National Science Foundation or Swedish Research Council. It tends to be the kind of grants that go to university researchers, people like us, and then gets distributed.

We're not looking at, for example, funding for consultancies, including everything from the World Bank and [United Nations Development Program] UNDP to smaller consultancies or privately funded research, which often have a research component to them. You may end up with a slightly different picture if you include other types of funding.

In terms of thinking about the research funding that is going to universities: First of all, yes, it is definitely the case that research funding in Europe and in the United States, at least until very recently, has far outstripped what there is in the region. It's also worth remembering that so has just the preponderance of researchers. So, you're looking, in the region, at a lot of universities that don't even have social science departments. Social sciences, unsurprisingly, are not where authoritarian regimes invest a lot of energy or national resources. According to the [2021 UNESCO Science Report](#), research investment by Arab states is quite low relative to other regions, and it's even lower when it comes to research investment into social sciences. So, when you take all of those things into account, you find that the vast majority of research funding for the type of research that most academics do is coming out of the US and Europe.

It's not very surprising that these countries are interested in funding the research that they think matters to them. We would expect national interests to drive funding. But the focus on national interests means that political science dominates European- and US-based research, and that there is greater emphasis on issues like migration in European-funded research and security issues in research funded from the US. The problem isn't necessarily that Europeans are interested in migration because they think that has implications for

them, or that the US is interested in what they see as security issues because they want to inform their foreign policy. We should anticipate that.

The problem arises because there is an imbalance in the sources of resources for research and this creates an imbalance in terms of what gets understood. The topics that people in the region care about are not necessarily the topics that then get studied. If you look at what sort of research appears to be of interest to researchers in the Middle East, North Africa, or [Southwest Asia and North Africa] SWANA region, you're seeing that it's environmental and social issues, and other things that we don't really see prioritized.

So to me, it's interesting to think about how a potential longer term decline of US-based funding will affect our understanding of the region. Does it mean that you'll see an uptick of funding from elsewhere? Does it mean that basically we just see much less knowledge being generated in English about the SWANA region to begin with? I'm not entirely sure. I think that's something we can all discuss.

The other thing I want to highlight, which is less about research funding but is really important to think through, is how we understand the knowledge landscape itself. These big gaps in knowledge are not only about donor priorities and research funding; they are also about what reviewers think is important and what gets rewarded if you are going up for tenure, for example. So, it's not simply the US government's interest or European governments' interests, but also scholars' priorities, that shape our knowledge.

Finally, I want to note that research being done in various places, such as in consultancies or international organizations, is often

not made public. Most of us don't see that research or its results. That is an important type of gap when trying to better understand research production in and on the region.

DG: Yeah, thanks for that. It is also worth noting that, in this article, you are looking at relatively recent grant awards from 2016 to 2021. But, in terms of some of those general observations, which among these are more recent and which are maybe longer-term trends? For example, this regional imbalance in terms of the sources of social science funding, and also, as Ellen's pointing out, a lot of the results of research on MENA do not ultimately make it into the public sphere, or into scholarly publications, and it's sort of hidden from view.

Lisa Anderson (LA): Actually, as I was thinking about this, I don't think that funding for research, probably anywhere and ever, but particularly in my professional life around the Middle East, has ever not been driven by political imperatives. The conceit that we spend a lot of time fostering – that there was something that was completely independent research, and that had no political context or motive – you know... that clearly was wrong, always, and forever. So, then the question is: are there differences now in sources of funding that will reflect different kinds of political interests? If the United States in general is going to be funding less, will that be reflected just in volume – will there just be less research? – or will the political coloration of the research that's done change?

So I think there are going to be a variety of subsidiary questions, but one question I don't think we should spend much time on is whether there are political agendas in research. There clearly are, and there always have been, and American foundations, when

they were funding, they could be sort of adjacent to government funding, but they were not unaffected by government funding, even in the best, most politically pluralistic moments. For instance, I was early to understand that, since I could not get a Fulbright to go to Libya because the American government said no, at the end of the day, I was in one of those sort of pluralistic moments when the Social Science Research Council was funding dissertation research, and they were willing to fund my travel. But, you know, that SSRC funding came from big foundations, that came from the Ford Foundation. Ford, in the intervening decades, has been, among many other foundations, under enormous pressure not to fund what could be construed as support of terrorist organizations, or even “terrorist sympathizers,” through laws on money-laundering, sanctions, and so forth. So, the space to be adjacent to the American government, supplementing and widening the research landscape, has shrunk. Partly as a result major foundations have turned to less contentious arenas and particularly to back-filling where the US government is no longer supporting work domestically.

But in any event, I think some of these conditions have been familiar to us for a long time, and some of them have become more constraining.

DG: Yeah, I think we could probably identify some turning points or key moments.

LA: 9/11 made a big difference.

DG: Yeah. Salma, Go ahead.

SALMA MOUSA (SM): Yeah, thank you. It's really nice to be in all of your company, and to hear all of this.

I just wanted to raise two points. The first is when we say a lot of this funding of MENA research comes from abroad, I think one somewhat unfortunate thing is that there are actually pockets in the Middle East that have a lot of money that they could be spending on research funding. The Doha Institute, [and its affiliated Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies,] for example, and other big institutes in the Gulf that are kind of half think tank but also have graduate programs. They are research- and teaching-oriented, and presumably have money to be funding international, competitive grants. They have launched large-scale data collection initiatives too, like the [Arab Opinion Index](#), so there is an appreciation of quantitative research. But given the way that field experiments and large-scale quantitative work has evolved in the U.S., there may be an underappreciation of how much it costs to do research that requires collecting original data at scale, and I think that's unfortunate.

My second point is regarding these big funders from the US, the UK, and Europe like [the Abdul Latif Jameel Poverty Action Lab] J-PAL, Innovations for Poverty Action, or Center for Economic Policy Research. They have money, and they fund projects on the Middle East, but they get to decide, of course, their priority countries. And it's always kind of unclear to me how those countries are chosen. This year, it's Syria and Turkey and Yemen. So, if you have a project on, for instance, Egypt, that's not a priority country. There could be some more transparency into the process of determining priority countries, and where there is, it's often tied to the policy priorities of the funding government or organization. I actually once tried to submit a proposal for a project funded by the British foreign ministry, that would have included a component in the West Bank, and

the donor rejected it, saying we don't fund work in "developed countries", basically implying that the West Bank was Israel. So, that's at the extreme end, but I think this classification of priority countries, and what's considered a developing country versus developed, takes away a lot of power from researchers, I think, to pursue what they think is good work. And it's really unfortunate that even those who do have the money in the Middle East are not actually funding research grants, which would, I think, help a lot.

DG: Yeah, thanks for that perspective, Salma, since some of those institutions are, not necessarily ones that we would have centrally considered otherwise, J-PAL and others, like the World Bank, for example. And maybe that's something to acknowledge as well in this conversation, is that different institutions have different sorts of knowledge bases about the region, and ways that they do or do not understand politics in the region, and then that shapes their priorities. Economists, for example, will come from a different knowledge base and different perspective.

SM: Yeah, that's a whole other conversation. But, I think sometimes it can be good to have people who are doing work on the region who actually don't have as much country-specific knowledge. Sometimes it helps when you take a step back and just treat it as any other country, in a way. Not always, but sometimes. For example, there is [this paper by Bursztyn et al.](#) about correcting misperceptions about social norms about female labor market participation in Saudi Arabia. Basically, most men think that other men are not cool with their wives and sisters working, but, in fact, most of them are pretty cool with it. So, once you tell them that, their wives and sisters are more likely to apply for jobs. And I think it's a really cool paper. It's published in

the [American Economic Review] AER, a top economics journal.

And I have seen certain takedowns of [randomized controlled trials] RCTs in the Middle East, and they don't really critique the substance of the studies. Some studies, like the one I mentioned, actually did something that was probably helpful in that society. So, I think it can be unfortunate when we restrict ourselves in that way. There is some good work about the Middle East, not necessarily by Middle Eastern researchers, that comes from that economics perspective. I think there are some problems with it, for sure, but well-articulated critiques of these problems should deal with the substance of the research.

EL: What I think both Lisa and Salma's comments suggest is the importance of pluralism – whether we're talking about pluralism in funding, or we're talking about pluralism in methodologies, countries, or the perspectives from which people approach these various problems. And I think that the real concern is when you lose that. We shouldn't expect any funder, whether it's the World Bank or governments or foundations, to be funding outside of their interests. So, the important question is how many different interests can be at the table, providing funding?

Yes, the institutions in the Gulf can do more, but, more generally, I think it's good to have a variety and a wide range of approaches and interests coming into the landscape.

SM: Also, I just remembered that J-PAL actually opened an office at [the American University in Cairo] AUC. So there's a J-PAL MENA office now, which I think is huge, and they are funding work all across the Middle East. They're based in Cairo, and you can

draw on their resources. So, for example, the [Institutional Review Board] IRB research managers that they assign you will be based in Egypt to help run the project.

They even supported qualitative researchers for our project, so they sent people all over Egypt to do interviews with our research participants. So, they weren't so dogmatic about the approach. They were really open to adding these qualitative components, and that's really nice, because that's completely administered by people at AUC. Funding opportunities here include the Air and Water lab at the Hub of Advanced Policy Innovation for the Environment ([HAPIE](#)), and the [Egypt Impact Lab](#). Yes, it is tied a little bit still to the economic development perspective. And the goals have to somewhat be aligned with goals that the Egyptian government is okay with – for example, outcomes like health and education and family planning. You can't be too risky. But if your research happens to fall within that bucket, that's a bright spot I want to highlight for others, because I don't think enough people know about it. I think they actually have quite a lot of funding.

DG: Thanks for that. We have a diverse readership, so, you know, I think we're hoping that junior scholars reading the newsletter can benefit from some of these insights, tips, and perspectives.

Sofia Fenner (SF): It's really interesting to hear all of these sort of institutional perspectives, because I think I approached this question very differently, which was a question about what researchers do given certain challenges, one of which is funding, but I think just to name the thing, the biggest challenge is authoritarianism. That has always been the biggest challenge, and that remains the biggest challenge, I think, for both scholars in

the region and scholars outside of the region, and that hasn't changed.

So, from a qualitative perspective, and really from an interpretive perspective, I think that one of the great virtues of certain kinds of qualitative research is that they are cheap—relatively cheap—and also relatively adaptable to circumstances. Often, especially at an early career stage, the only thing a researcher really needs is a plane ticket and somewhere to live. That's the kind of funding that you can cobble together from all kinds of sources; you don't need massive grants that can really only come from institutions or governments, whether in the region or outside of it. If you speak the dialect that you need to speak to be doing the research that you're doing, you don't need to hire a translator. You don't need to hire an interpreter. Again, to Lisa's point, independent research has always been sort of a fiction, but I think there are ways to make research cheaper, and thereby maybe construct a certain kind of autonomy. It won't work for everybody, and it won't work for all methods, but I think this is one of those moments when certain kinds of qualitative methods really have an advantage: that they simply don't cost as much money as a randomized controlled trial, or a survey, or some of this really fascinating, scaled work that, unfortunately, is very expensive.

Historical research can also be inexpensive if you can get to an archive, or if the archive is available somewhere that you can access. Even if you can't get local government approval, or you can't get a lot of funding from US or European institutions, you might still be able to get access to archival materials. Many qualitative researchers will say, “Yeah, I'm a comparative historical researcher,” but are we actually trained as historians? Do we actually have the skills required to work with

primary sources? Because once we have those skills, we're empowered to do kinds of research that can slip under the radar in certain ways while still speaking to central social science questions.

Thinking about ways that we can continue to generate knowledge and continue to have conversations in a world where we have fewer funding sources involves taking a look at not just qualitative methods, but also interpretive epistemologies and ontologies.

So, for example, sometimes when you're dealing with a difficult funding situation, or a difficult political situation, or both, there happens to be a place you can go and learn *something*, but you don't necessarily know what it is yet. That situation isn't going to meet positivist standards of case selection, or representativeness, or any of those other things. And the discipline's not super well positioned, and especially young scholars are often not well positioned, to defend or accept the knowledge production capacity of a research design that's honest about its origins: "This was a place I could go at a time where I had money to be there, and I didn't really know what I was going to find, and this is what I found." We should be open to funding projects that might be less structured in their research design and that are open to responding to local political conditions. Maybe you did have a relationship with a local institution, and maybe that disintegrates for any of a variety of reasons. What does ethics look like now?

I'm thinking about how we can build, for lack of a better word, scrappiness into research designs, and how we can respect and honor research designs that have that scrappiness. And really acknowledge the ways in which such projects contribute to knowledge accu-

mulation.

For me, not so much because of funding, but

because of politics, that's the direction that I am moving towards. Safe, ethical, ethnographic research in the region seems like it is becoming more and more difficult. One of the ways we can cope with that is to move to the past in a really meaningful sense: to work with primary sources, ask questions about "the archive," and maybe become a little more comfortable with uncertainty. If political science becomes de-emphasized because of a lack of funding from the United States, maybe history, anthropology—other kinds of approaches many of us are adjacent to already—move in to take up some of that space. Maybe this is a time to lean in that direction, and to collaborate across borders, but also across disciplines. Historians never have enough money to make it to the past. No one can go to the past! I think there's a lot of potential there.

We are sort of a magpie discipline. We like to steal other disciplines' methods and adapt them to our own purposes. It might be a good time to lean into methods that are more "instability-proof" – I don't know if that's the right term for it – but methods that give us a little bit more maneuvering room, no matter where we are, or who we are.

EL: Can I chime in here? I recognize this might be taking us a little bit afar, but what I like about that, Sofia, is that it's not just about historical research being less expensive. The challenge in the way that we've done things in political science is that we are often responding to the immediate crisis and need. 9/11 happened, and we all wanted to study radical Islamists. Then something else happens, and

we all want to study whatever the next wave is. But essentially, we are not well situated to study radical Islamists in the moment when they're at their height and before anything else changes. And by the time we're starting to see some interesting changes among Islamist movements and radical Islam, then we've all moved on to something else. So, the advantage of studying the past is that we can actually do what, in a sense, we should be doing anyway – really be studying from a perspective where we can more easily separate trajectories and have a better understanding of the fuller picture of the things that we study. So I think there's an argument to be made that goes beyond the funding, logistics, and what's feasible and to really think about how incorporating a historical perspective may help us actually change the way in which we gain knowledge and understand it. It doesn't work for everything, but for some things, it might be superior.

SF: Yes! I am at a small liberal arts college (SLAC) that is primarily and overwhelmingly focused on undergraduate teaching, and that obviously creates some research and funding challenges of its own. But I think it also opens up certain possibilities. For example, we have very different tenure expectations, so there's nothing wrong with publishing as a political scientist primarily in non-political science journals, i.e. in area studies journals, historical journals, literary studies journals, or anywhere else. At certain universities, that would be a real career problem. But in other places it's not; indeed, it's sometimes seen as a virtue!

It's odd because I'm used to looking with a certain amount of envy at the research support that's available at research-oriented institutions and universities. But I've come to appreciate the flexibility afforded by a differ-

ent way of approaching career incentives. In navigating this funding environment, being at a SLAC feels very much like a privilege right now. I think it would be very difficult if I were somewhere where the tenure standards expected me to do very large-scale work very quickly and publish it only in political science journals. I would be feeling a lot more uncertain than I am now.

In fact, thinking about where knowledge lives and how it's reproduced, and where it's stored and conserved during periods of difficulty, might also invite us to think a little bit differently about the role of different kinds of institutions, both here and elsewhere, in knowledge production.

DG: Thank you, Sofia and Ellen as well for that, and I want to welcome Jamil, who was having some electricity issues, but has now rejoined us. Welcome.

JAMIL MOUAWAD (JM): Again, thanks for having me. One issue that I think is important to highlight is the role of the IRB and the concepts of risk. Of course, I'm speaking to you from the region, and here we are caught between the imperatives of the IRB and the reality we live in. Risk is part of our daily life. So, assessing risk from the vantage point of the IRB might differ entirely from how we, in our context and experience, feel and perceive it. And this lens is a tool now, I'm afraid, that contributes to the construction of the region as a “security threat”. So, of course, the region is a threat for some researchers. We've seen some very unfortunate incidents with PhD students in Egypt, for example, and elsewhere in the region, but it doesn't mean that we only have to look at the region from a risk perspective, or from a threat perspective. The IRBs as institutions were essentially designed in the West and

then traveled to, and land in, our institutions here. They tend to approach the region through a security lens, thereby shaping it as a site of potential threat. So the IRB has an impact, which is constructing the region as a security threat, and contributing to over-scrutinizing the region at the same time.

The threat that an IRB committee member sometimes sees is in fact my daily life – my daily reality. So imagine Arab students working on their PhDs in Europe or in the US and they are not granted permission to go and do their fieldwork while their parents live here, or even to come and stay for holidays. So there is a discrepancy between the requirements and the way the IRB looks at the region and the reality of the region. And this should be addressed. This is [the work we've been doing](#) at the Arab Council for Social Sciences (ACSS), in a way – trying to move away from treating ethics as just a checklist and look, rather, at indigenous understanding of ethics.

Let's look at ethics as situational, as an encounter, and not only as a tool to give a green or red light to what to do, what topics we should work on, and whatnot.

And the second point that I would like to raise is that ethics can sometimes be used as an alibi to censor research, whether by governments, universities, or even professors. They take advantage of this, and they do censor research by saying it has to go through the IRB. So, the IRB here is no longer a tool to safeguard the researcher and protect participants. It's also a tool to censor research, to control what kind of questions can be asked, and what kind of knowledge is acceptable or not. This is very unfortunate.

The third point I'd like to make is that I've

had many students, for example, students working on their MA thesis, and they avoid the IRB, because it takes a lot of time and the application is way too long. So they end up relying on secondary resources for their MAs, and we're missing a very good opportunity to produce original research, from students who are based in the region and in the field, and can indeed produce very original analysis that is otherwise not always accessible for those who are studying the region but are not based in the region. Instead, students end up being disconnected from the field – even though they live in the region – because simply the IRB becomes too cumbersome and time-consuming. They want to graduate to go on the job market. So, there is an imperative to rethink IRB. Of course, it doesn't mean that we should not be part of the promotion of the culture of ethics in social sciences and humanities, especially in the Arab world. We need it, but it shouldn't act as a tool to censor research and prevent the production of original knowledge.

And funding is part of this, because I know at the ACSS that they require applicants to fill out a questionnaire on ethics. This is a good thing to do, but again, it shouldn't be a reason why we grant or we don't grant access to the field. Because already those researchers are in the field. Risk is there. Risk, as I said, is part of their everyday life.

SF: On this note, I think it's less common for qualitative researchers who go through an IRB process to have a local IRB partner, partly because the simple fact of that is actually exposing everyone involved to more risk than they might otherwise be exposed to.

That is part of why there needs to be a robust discussion, especially among qualitative researchers, about the ethics of what we're

doing and how we're doing it. There needs to be real dialogue about what informed consent means and about information practices, because honestly, the IRB system in the United States doesn't hold certain kinds of qualitative research to as high a standard as I think it should. Partly because it doesn't really recognize them as valid forms of research, right? What harm could possibly come of just asking people questions and listening to the answers? The IRB system isn't designed for that kind of research or for the dangers it poses.

LA: I'd just like to follow up a little bit on this, and Sofia, I think you're a little bit more generous about this than I'm about to be. It's really about risk management for the institutions. It's not, in fact, about ethics or even risk management for individual researchers. Honestly, I don't think most of the institutions that have IRBs care very much about the safety and security of the researchers. They just know that it's bad for reputation management if something happens to somebody. So it's almost hostile to research. You know, it's sort of, "We have to let you do it, because we're supposed to let you do it, but life would be much easier if none of you did research." And so let's narrow it as much as possible, make it as "safe" as possible, and make it as risk-free as possible.

There's an almost self-defeating quality in some of the ways IRBs, and General Counsel's offices, operate these days, because you can see that they would just prefer nobody did any research, because somehow it's going to be a problem for them. So, I think this is a fundamental problem, and I don't see how, as IRBs are currently constructed, that they would be able to absorb the scrappiness in the kinds of research that Sofia was encouraging earlier. I just don't see how they're going

to be able to say, "Yeah, go ahead and see what happens." I mean, that's not how they're designed at this point.

So I think we need to think about the various gatekeepers for research. One of them is IRBs and the institutions that are supposed to be fostering research. Another is, of course, funders. Funders are going to foster the kind of research that they think is valuable, but it may not be the kind of research that any of us want to do. There are a bunch of gatekeepers of research and we can't be totally free-wheeling and do what we want, for a variety of reasons. In fact, I think that the environment for research has actually become more constrained over time. So, yeah, I did a comparative study of Tunisia and Libya, not because I had an elegant comparative research design but because I needed a fall-back since I wasn't sure I'd get a visa to Libya. Full stop.

That's not a good argument for the comparison, but it was the underlying rationale for the comparison, and then I developed something that I thought made a great deal of sense. And, in fact, I found things I didn't expect. I would never have been able to tell the IRB that. I do think the context, the institutional framework for research, has become quite deliberately discouraging.

So, Diana, if I may, I think one of the things that has come up as a productive way of looking at this is a kind of bricolage. You know: maybe you can do something with J-PAL, maybe you can do something in the archives, and so forth. It rests with the researcher to be creative about that, to learn that this kind of work would be possible in Egypt if I work with J-PAL, or this might be possible in Libya if I can get into the archives, et cetera.

I think there are opportunities like that to be

creative. However, there are two difficulties that I would flag. First, it really does burden the researcher to be not only intellectually creative, but also institutionally knowledgeable to figure out where the space is. For example, you can work on climate, and maybe you'll get some funding because the climate people have some money...All of us need to be thinking in that way more than we typically do. We're just sort of waiting for the funding to come to do whatever we want, and that's obviously not happening. So it does burden the researcher a little, you know. I'm thinking of early-career people doing their PhDs trying to figure out where these opportunities are.

The second question is an ethical issue. If this is a productive approach to, for example, tag along with the World Bank, or tag along with J-PAL, or tag along with some other organization, to what extent are you being completely candid with the people you're tagging along with about the research you're doing? Is it shaping, or even distorting or warping, what you want to do, and to what extent are you being candid, even with yourself, about that? Because these opportunities are genuinely there, but they may also be [what Sarah Parkinson calls](#) "dual hatting." So, for example, you are going out as an embed in the military in Iraq and doing your PhD at the same time. Is that okay? Or, more ambiguously, what if you're doing something as a consultant? What are the guidelines there, not only for IRBs, but for ourselves, so that we can say, "Everybody knows what I am doing, everybody knows why I am doing it, everybody knows this is what I might contribute to the larger project, and this is where the limits of my contributions are going to be. Everybody knows that I am going to publish this, whatever the terms of the funders are." I think there's going to be more and more of that

kind of arrangement, and we haven't entirely thought through how to provide guidance on what that relationship should look like as a junior early career person interacts with that research institution and with their home department. So I think there are opportunities, but they are also going to be providing us with new questions.

EL: I agree with much of what you say, Lisa. How do we understand what the real opportunities are, what does it mean to be consulting, and frankly, what are some of the challenges with that?

You know, sometimes you feel perfectly fine with the project you are on, and you feel perfectly fine with the expectations, and you have been very upfront about the fact that you will use this data to publish. And the organization you are working with says, "That's great, and that can be done as soon as we have published our own report," and then, for internal political reasons, they decide never to do that. So, then you are basically up a creek. You have essentially subsidized a relatively powerful organization and suddenly you are out of luck because you can't use the data.

Scholars trying to navigate these relationships benefit from the kinds of conversations and communities that [the Research Ethics in the Middle East and North Africa \(REME-NA\) project](#) has built and is building, that [the Project on Middle East Political Science \(POMEPS\)](#) has built and is building. That's great for everybody who has access to those conversations. However, lots of PhD students working on the region are actually not in places where their advisors know the region or are well-connected to these communities. So, I think we need to consider how we, as a community, can make sure that we are not

just reaching those PhD students whose advisors can connect them into POMEPS or REMENA, for example, but we are including people who are not at those institutions. How can we commit ...to make sure that the impact doesn't remain within a smaller set of people who are interested and care about the region, but rather expand these conversations to a fuller set of young scholars?

SF: But also, Lisa and Ellen, hearing you talk about this just makes me think: This discussion is itself a fascinating social science topic! How do people generate knowledge in circumstances where funding is constrained, where freedom of choice and expression are constrained, where there are power imbalances involved that are really important? The people who have the most experience with trying to do research under those circumstances are scholars in the region.

So, I think this is a really interesting opportunity to say: Well, how have the scholars I know in Egypt historically navigated conflicts of interest, or those “double-hatting” situations? How have they honored the principle of transparency when they can't necessarily be transparent vis-a-vis their governments? And how do they think about the ethics of that? Those of us who have had the privilege of working in relatively open environments have a lot to learn from those who haven't.

LA: I just have one quick crack about that, if I may, because I completely agree with you. I have been corresponding with a Libyan colleague about some work that we're doing together. I apologized to him for being distracted, because, as we all know, Columbia University has been in a lot of upheaval. He wrote back and said, “Yeah, it's been like that here for 45 years.”

DG: These reflections and guidance are all really helpful. If we look at some of REMENA's recommendations, we see that they are geared toward trying to promote more collaboration with institutions and scholars based in the region, and to have those forms of collaboration be supported throughout the whole ecosystem, funding included. So, I think getting a sense of the climate for social science research in the region would be really helpful for this discussion. Jamil, I certainly don't intend to make you a representative of the MENA region, but...

JM: Yes, I am “the local.” [laughs]

DG: [laughs] Right. But I do have questions about this. Maybe you can give us a sense of what it looks like for PhD students or junior faculty members in MENA trying to get social science research support. Earlier in the conversation, we touched on the role of some of the big academic institutes in Doha and elsewhere in the Gulf, for example. But, across the region as a whole, what role do different types of universities and research institutions play in, in funding or supporting – or not funding and not supporting – social science research?

JM: I mean, Doha and the Gulf is one set of cases, and then other universities in, for example, Egypt, Palestine, and Lebanon, maybe this is another set of cases where funds and resources are less available; partially because of the political economy of these countries and the ongoing political crises, including refugee displacement, wars, and even instances of genocide. These problems, to a certain extent, define the knowledge we produce. The knowledge production is now dictated to a certain extent by funding, and those who are being funded the most are NGOs or think tanks. This is based on the assumption that

their reports can be produced quickly and are necessary to address such pressing issues and challenges. This has implications on the kind of knowledge we produce, and the reality we are constructing.

So, it's a fairly easy way to go and get money, and then you produce research and knowledge that does not always have the same methodological rigor as studies that follow academic criteria. Maybe this research is not ethical in itself. For instance, imagine the number of reports that were published by NGOs on refugees with no ethical consideration whatsoever. Most of these reports are not peer-reviewed – I'm talking here about international, but also local and national, NGOs. Funding at the university looks far more complicated, and it's more challenging to obtain than funding at an NGO or an international organization. So here, I refer to the point that Lisa brought up, which is working as a consultant. At the end of the day, given the political economy of the region and the political economy of our profession, you might end up accepting to work as a consultant for a UN agency, and this introduces completely different parameters for doing research, because you know that you have to write something that they would eventually accept, which secures for you yet another consultancy. In some instances, we lose the purpose of knowledge, which is to speak truth to power. It is a completely different framework than what we use when publishing in a peer-reviewed journal, or presenting a paper in an academic conference. This has an impact on knowledge production. It is an epistemological question. In the region right now, it is often far easier for me to go and write a report for a NGO than to, for example, get funds to do fieldwork for an article that I would submit to a peer-reviewed journal; an article that takes two years to produce

and another one to publish.

A second point is that we should acknowledge that “the field” is not accessible in the region, or at least it is less and less accessible, due to wars in places like Syria, Lebanon, Palestine, and Yemen. But there is also a way to look at the field not as a physical space, but also the field as bricolage, and I'm using the word here offered earlier by Lisa. Bricolage means we need to rethink and be creative on how we construct the field by assembling different methods and techniques, even if we're not in this region. We need to gather different sets of methods and construct our own field. So someone living in the US working on Palestine, he or she cannot access the field, that's for sure, but they can recruit local researchers, train local researchers, they can do digital anthropology, et cetera. So we really need to be creative when it comes to trying to construct our own fields. And this is often not fully appreciated or captured by donors. They are used to mainstream political science that is very much based on quantitative research, but we do need to be creative and carve out more space for interpretivist approaches to the field.

So, this is something scholars in the region have been thinking about a lot. The field as bricolage, as Lisa puts it, and as an alternative to field inaccessibility. Here, we can talk more about partnerships between those who are in the US or Europe and us local scholars or researchers working in the region. So we have to be creative in this sense.

DG: We are running up against the clock, but another thing we haven't touched on are other research methods that are generally less expensive. This includes work that is remotely based, maybe computationally intensive, perhaps even using newly digitized archival

sources, or things that you can do a little bit more easily. And so, in a sense, that is a very different approach, but it ties into this idea that Jamil is referencing of reinterpreting the field and what becomes “the field” for us in these circumstances. Any thoughts on that, Salma, or others?

SM: Yes. Well, at UCLA we have even less research funding than we had before, so when I'm advising graduate students, I do encourage them to consider learning how to use these AI tools for scraping social media, websites, administrative data, and the like. There is a lot of free data. Go to the [World Values Survey](#), go to the [Arab Barometer](#), go to the general social surveys, the [Gallup World Poll](#), et cetera. There is so much data out there. Learn to scrape newspaper articles, do a sentiment analysis, code up how people are talking about certain topics. Even if you are doing qualitative interviews: For example, if you conduct interviews with 50 people, and there is a roughly 20-page transcript for each person, you can actually code up what people are talking about, you can systematically label them using ChatGPT and tools like that, and all of that is basically free. So I'm really moving students to try to find data that is already out there in the world, and just learn the skills to actually use that stuff. We don't have much funding anymore anyway, and this data is really rich and probably underexplored. It is highly unstructured, and this unstructured data is where we get so much leverage from AI, as opposed to survey data, for example. I know I mentioned survey data as well, but this unstructured data – like images and text – those are the kinds of things where researchers, especially if they know Arabic and they are able to adapt these tools, it's really underexplored. So, I definitely push students in that direction if they're interested in learning those methods.

LA: I completely endorse this. One of the things that all of us, collectively, need to be thinking more about is how all of our fields and research agendas are going to be reshaped by artificial intelligence and what you can do with it. That said, while the data itself might be largely unstructured, I don't think any of those AI tools are “unstructured”. They've been structured by somebody else. So, for example, you can scrape web data in Egypt, which is terrific, and I have students who have done that and it's been very instructive, but that means that you are operating at the level of the web. And there are a fair number of people in Egypt who don't live on the web, even now. So, you have to, as a student, say, “Yes, all of this stuff is available, but what is it bringing with it? What are the algorithms doing? What is the uneven availability of this technology doing?” So, as I said, I endorse this idea that we all ought to be exploring this, but I think we shouldn't be behind a veil of ignorance here. There are built-in characteristics to these sorts of data and analytic tools that we need to acknowledge, and perhaps utilize to our benefit. Pretending those structures are not there can lead to reproducing some of the biases that are built in, rather than acknowledging and using them.

DG: Thank you, Salma and Lisa. Are there any other threads we want to tie up before concluding?

JM: May I add one point, actually? I mean, we are living in a crisis, us, those who are here in the region, and producing knowledge and doing research on your own predicament and struggles is often very challenging. At times, this even becomes absurd. I have witnessed this firsthand with the economic and financial collapse in Lebanon. I mean, what would I study? I would only study my very own misery. So, this is something that we all

have to be aware of, let alone the wars and extreme violence that others are experiencing.

The pressure on us to publish, is in itself an ethical question worth raising. Those of us who live in the region place expectations on ourselves (not to make ourselves victims, far from it), but... again, it remains profoundly difficult to study your own misery. Yet, sometimes it looks extremely superficial for others to come and study your own misery, and you become the subject of their research instead of the one who should produce knowledge that is indigenous, in terms of emotions, in terms of tools, techniques, and methods. So this is something to consider. A general comment.

DG: Absolutely. I think that's a really constructive point for all of us to keep in mind. As someone who has done work on Palestine now, it feels almost unethical, or at least ethically complex, to do any research from here that is about people experiencing a genocide while we watch. And, as you've alluded to, some voices from Palestine have been present in popular analysis and news media and such, but in research, you know, are we going to have those voices? How much research will we have in our field, going forward, that's being produced by Palestinians and by Palestinian survivors or those with close connections to survivors?

JM: So there is a gap now between those who can produce and those who cannot.

DG: Right. I want to thank you all again for generously dedicating your time and intellect to this very fruitful discussion.